

Appendix 2. Protocol for examining user experience

Background

There is increasing recognition of the importance of patients' and public involvement in decision making about their health and healthcare. However, these groups, as well as healthcare professionals and policymakers, need information about the effects of interventions to make informed decisions about healthcare. To be useful and usable, this information must be easily accessible, understandable, and reliable.

During the Coronavirus 2019 pandemic (COVID-19) the public (at the individual level and societal level) were inundated with ever-changing regulations, recommendations, and advice (REF). It was not always clear why, how, or by whom public health regulations, recommendations and advice were formed. While the current research team has long been interested in the effects of interventions to improve informed health choices among the public (IHC REF), this pandemic highlighted the importance of public health messages and how public health officials communicate with the public.

A group of researchers from the Norwegian Institute of Public Health and the Dartmouth Institute for Health Policy and Clinical Practice have initiated a project to set up and test a platform to facilitate user testing and randomized controlled trials of the effects of public health messages on the understanding of the messages, beliefs, and effects of the messages on decisions, intended behaviours or actual behaviours.

Communicating certainty of evidence

As part of the first phase of the development of Message Lab, the research team has planned a randomized controlled trial to examine the effect of communicating certainty of evidence related to the effects (benefit and downsides) of an intervention. Certainty of evidence refers to "the extent of our confidence that the estimates of the effect are correct or are adequate to support a particular decision or recommendation" (Balshem, Helfand et al. 2011). We estimate certainty of evidence by conducting GRADE assessments of individual review findings (based on assessments of risk of bias, indirectness, inconsistency, imprecision, and publication bias (Balshem 2011)). More recently, the GRADE working group has clarified what certainty of evidence refers to by stating that "when rating certainty of the evidence for an individual outcome, we are rating how certain we are that the true effect lies within a particular range or on one side of a threshold." (Hultcrantz, Rind et al. 2017). Traditionally, we have communicated certainty of evidence by presenting a pictorial representation of certainty (e.g., ⊕⊕○○) along with a statement related to certainty (low certainty). We have also provided information in some documents (e.g., full systematic reviews) regarding these assessments (e.g., summary of findings tables and evidence profiles) (REF).

Certainty is communicated two ways when writing a public health message or summarizing the evidence related to an intervention. Firstly, we communicate our certainty in the evidence related to benefit and downsides of the intervention by stating the certainty of the evidence in parentheses and providing a visual representation (see examples in Table 1). This standard current practice (within Cochrane and the Norwegian Institute of Public Health) is based on guidance from the Cochrane Effective Organization of Care group (EPOC). The EPOC guidance and format was developed using stakeholder feedback, surveys, and user testing (Glenton, Underland et al. 2006, Santesso, Glenton et al. 2009, Glenton, Santesso et al. 2010, Woloshin and Schwartz 2011).

Table 1. Standardized statements for reporting certainty of evidence for important benefit or downsides of an intervention (adapted from ((EPOC). 2018))

High certainty evidence ⊕⊕⊕⊕	[Intervention] improves/reduces [outcome] (high certainty evidence)
Moderate certainty evidence ⊕⊕⊕○	[Intervention] probably improves/reduces [outcome] (moderate certainty evidence)
Low certainty evidence ⊕⊕○○	[Intervention] may improve/reduce [outcome] (low certainty evidence)
Very low certainty evidence ⊕○○○	We don't know if/It is uncertain whether [intervention] improves/reduces [outcome] because the certainty of this evidence is very low.

Secondly, we communicate certainty by providing confidence intervals for the effect size of a benefit or downside. A confidence interval is defined as “the range of values that we observe in our sample and for which we expect to find the value that accurately reflects the population” (DePoy and Gitlin 2016). Confidence interval is also sometimes referred to as the margin of error. An example of reporting a confidence interval or margins of error is “SMD=1.4, (0.8, 1.9)” or “the effect size is estimated to be 1.4, however the true effect size may be between 0.8 and 1.9.”

In the planned randomized controlled trial, we will present a health message to address the question What is the effect of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting covid? Some observational studies have indicated that there is an association between use of glasses and a reduced risk of contracting covid (Maxcy 1919, Chu, Akl et al. 2020, Jefferson, Del Mar et al. 2020, Byambasuren, Beller et al. 2021, Coroneo and Collignon 2021). A randomized controlled trial was conducted to examine this effect (Fretheim, Hemkens et al. 2022), and the results will be adapted for this trial and presented to stakeholders to examine the effect of different versions of the public health message on their understanding of the health message, and corresponding intended or actual behaviours. The trial will use a 3 (standard certainty of evidence statement vs colloquial certainty of evidence statement vs no certainty of evidence statement) x 2 (margin of error text vs no margin of error text) between-subjects design.

Prior to conducting the randomized trial, we will collect feedback through user testing from a small sample of people representing trial participants on the content and formatting of the messages that will be used in the trial to optimize the message content and format. We will use an adapted version of Morville’s Honeycomb model to guide user testing data collection and analysis (Morville , Rosenbaum 2010). This model provides facets of useability which can be used to categorize and organize user feedback and then refine aspects of a products to make it more user-friendly. See Figure 1 and Table 2 for an overview of the facets of the honeycomb model.

Figure 1. Adapted version of Morville’s honeycomb model (Rosenbaum 2010)

Table 2. Facets of user experience according to an adapted version of Morville’s honeycomb model (Rosenbaum (2010) (Rosenbaum 2010))

Facet of user experience	Definition
Findability	Can users locate what they are looking for?
Accessibility	Are there physical barriers to actually gaining access? Are there for people with disabilities?
Usability	How easy and satisfying is this product to use?
Usefulness	Does this product have practical value for this user?
Credibility	Is it trustworthy?
Desirability	Is it something the user wants? Has a positive emotional response to?
Value	Does this product support the individual, group, or institution using the product in achieving their goal(s)?
Affiliation*	Does the user feel that they are the appropriate audience for the product (i.e., is the product targeted to me)?
Understandability*	Does the user understand the content of the product?

*Added to Morville’s original honeycomb model by Rosenbaum (2010) (Rosenbaum 2010)

Aim

Our aim is to ensure that the language and format of the text to be used in the trial does not present additional burden or confounding factors when testing the effect of testing different modes of communicating certainty of evidence in the randomized controlled trial. Specifically, our objectives are:

- To gather feedback on the certainty statements and text related to communicating margins of error.

- To gather feedback on the full public health message text
- To gather feedback on all materials related to the process of participating in the randomized controlled trial (e.g., from invitation to participate to finishing the trial).

Our objectives are specifically to examine the user experience of the language and format of the text:

- Does the instructions text contain the necessary information for stakeholders to understand the questions being asked?
- Does the public health message text contain the necessary information for stakeholders to understand the questions being asked?
- Is the text formatted so that stakeholders can easily find the most important information?
- Can stakeholders easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?
- Is the text formatted so that it is perceived as reliable, easy to understand?
- Does the text facilitate stakeholders' perceptions that they are the intended target audience for the text?

Methods

Message Lab and the randomized controlled trial

This user test is intended to inform the development of a randomized controlled trial to examine the effect of communicating certainty of evidence in public health messages. This randomized controlled trial will be the first of a larger project to establish a platform for testing out public health messages effects on beliefs and behaviour (Message Lab). The development of the Message Lab platform will use a human-centred design approach whereby researchers collaborate closely with relevant stakeholders and target audiences (Witteman, 2015 #24) (see Box 1 for more information on human-centred design and user testing methods).

Prior to embarking on the user test phase of this project, the research team brainstormed questions related to uncertainties in how to communicate research. They then prioritized the question “how to communicate certainty of evidence” and chose to focus the public health message on the use of glasses to reduce infection of Covid-19 using findings from a randomized controlled trial (Fretheim 2022).

Box 1. User-centred design and user testing

User-centred design is a “philosophical and methodological approach to design, emphasizing creating solutions catering to the needs of the user (rather than requiring the user to adapt to the solution of the developer) and involving users in development” (Rosenbaum, Glenton et al. 2008). This approach hinges on an iterative approach whereby protocols are developed, stakeholder feedback is gathered, and appropriate changes to the protocol are made before again gathering stakeholder feedback (See Figure 2). This cycle can go on as many times as necessary to achieve the final product.

Starting point and planned phases

Figure 2. Adapted version of Witteman (2015) model of user-centred design (Witteman, Dansokho et al. 2015, Munthe-Kaas 2021)

Stakeholder feedback can be gained via various methods, including but not limited to interview, focus groups, observation, surveys, workshops or stakeholder brainstorming sessions (Munthe-Kaas 2021). In this project, we will employ stakeholder interviews and observation to gather users' perspective on the format and language of the public health texts that will ultimately be used in the Message Lab randomized controlled trial.

Think-aloud method

The "think-aloud" method encourages participants to voice their thoughts and decision-making processes as they read the text and consider the information presented to them (Rosenbaum 2010, Richardson, Mishuris et al. 2017).

Setting

User testing will take place digitally since the planned randomized controlled trial text will be conducted online. The participants can thus participate from a convenient location.

We will use the Loop11 platform to show the public health messages.

Moderated vs unmoderated

Moderated user tests have the advantage of having a researcher present to facilitate the test, guide the participants and answer any questions as they arise. However, moderated tests are more resource intensive in terms of time and money. Unmoderated tests have the advantage that they can be conducted anytime (which is useful when participants come from other time zones, for example) and they are less resource demanding as they do not require a researcher to present under every test. The disadvantage is that if participants encounter challenges during the user test, there is no one there to guide or answer questions and they may not complete the task (or complete it incorrectly) (UserTesting. 2022).

In the user test we will explore the possibility of conducting moderated vs unmoderated user tests. We will conduct moderated two user tests, and two unmoderated user tests before deciding how to proceed with the rest of the tests, and the trial.

Phases of user testing

In keeping with the human-centred design approach, we will conduct two phases of user testing. We will use qualitative methods to collect and analyse data.

Figure 2. Phases of user testing

Data collection

This user test (and the corresponding RCT) will also be translated to Norwegian and user tests will be conducted in Norwegian and English.

Phase 1

We will test two methods for conducting the user test, a moderated version and an unmoderated (see description below). In the unmoderated test, the user test will be the same as is described below, but where the researchers will not be facilitating the test and making observations in real time.

We will also initially test different platforms for user testing (see [Attachment 1](#)). Once we have established the preferred platform, we will continue the rest of the user tests on that platform.

Participants will be invited to a digital meeting. During the meeting we will request that cameras and microphones are turned on and unmuted throughout the user test. The meeting will not be recorded.

We will use “think-aloud” method (see description above) as well as a semi-structured interview guide to collect data.

Figure 3. Six versions of the public health message

During the user test

One researcher will run the user test while another researcher observes and takes detailed notes.

We will begin by introducing the task and presenting the scenario. We will explain that the goal of the randomized controlled trial we will conduct will be to examine the effect of communicating certainty of evidence in different ways.

We will then begin with the user test. Each participant will be asked to read a scenario introducing the idea of wearing glasses to reduce COVID risk:

Imagine you hear that glasses may reduce your chance of becoming infected with COVID. You go online to find out more information and find a website that says...

They will then be shown version M6 of the text. We will inform participants that they will be asked to read through the full text numerous times. First, we will ask them to skim the text and we will ask them for their first impression of the text. Next, we will ask them to read through the text as they normally would. Finally, the researcher will go through the text together with the participant, section by section.

See figure 3 for an overview of the six versions of the public health message to be included in the randomized trial (see **Appendix 3** for full text). All versions of the message include hyperlinks and hover links for relevant terms. During the course of all user tests, we will observe and record which hyperlinks or hover texts the participants engage with (i.e. click on or hover over).

For each reading of the text the observing researcher will make notes on what the participants impressions are, what words or concepts appear to be difficult or confusing, any formatting issues, and how the participants interact with the text. Following the readings, we will conduct a semi-structured interview using questions based on Morville's honeycomb framework described above. We will also ask for suggestions and recommendations for changes to the text.

The participants will then be presented with version M4 of the text. They will be asked for first impressions, and then to go through the text more closely and answer a set of questions using a semi-structured interview guide (see [Attachment 2](#)). They will be encouraged to click on or hover over any relevant text or terms when available.

Next, the participants will be presented with the opening text of version M1 (What is the effect? What are the harms?). Again, they will be asked for first impressions, and then to go through the text more closely and answer a set of questions using a semi-structured interview guide.

When the participants have gone through all versions of the text, we will then present them with the list of trial questions about the text. They will be asked to answer a set of questions regarding the language, content, and format of the questions (see [Appendix 6](#)). Finally, participants will be presented with a list of concepts that are available via hyperlinks and hover text.

In moderated user tests, the instructions and observations will occur in real time. In unmoderated user tests, the instructions will be written ([Attachment 3](#)), and the participants will be asked specific questions related to understanding, language, and format (not the questions that will be asked in the trial).

All text to be presented to participants will be translated to Norwegian for Norwegian participants. Translation will be done by a native Norwegian speaking member of the research team.

Phase 2

In phase 2, we will repeat the process outlined under phase one. The feedback collected during phase 2 will lead to the final version of the texts to be used in the randomized controlled trial.

Phase 3

In phase 3, we will user test the public health messages (as described in phase 1) along with all written material consumed during the process of participating in the RCT from invitation to participate to the end of the trial. Details on this phase will come later when other materials are developed.

Participants and recruitment

We will use purposive sampling to identify a broad range of participants representing various educational, literacy, and language backgrounds. We will use convenience and snowball sampling to recruit participants

We will invite participants via email. Since the text is intended to be read online, the user tests will be conducted digitally and thus participants can participate from a convenient location.

Data analysis

For each phase of the user test, we will summarize and synthesise observational and interview data from all participants. We will use thematic analysis to code the data, whereby we will first read the notes from the user tests and code sentences, ideas and expressions into themes using predefined codes (Ritchie and Spencer 2002). The coding frame will include (but not be limited to) the following codes:

- Some facets of the honeycomb model (acceptability, understandability, usability, usefulness, credibility, desirability, affiliation)
- Codes to rate seriousness of a finding (e.g., how disruptive/confusing/problematic an identified issue with the text is for the user) – critical, problematic, slightly problematic
- Codes to highlight positive aspects of the text (helpful, important, valuable)
- Codes related to concrete suggestions
- Codes related to the content or part of the text to which the participant remarks pertain
- New codes will be added as necessary.

We will use these themes to refine the texts that will then be presented to a new group of users.

We will also examine the following:

- Frequency of unique issues in each iteration of the user test
- Frequency of issues per participant
- Frequency of participants who encounter a unique issue (to identify whether we are improving a specific useability issue versus making overall usability improvements)

Ethical considerations

No information to identify individual participants will be gathered. The participants' contact information will only be used to set up appointments for user tests and will not be connected to notes from the user tests. We may recontact participants to present summarized findings to see if eventual changes to the text reflect the feedback we gathered. We will therefore not need to apply for ethical approval from REK or any other relevant board.

Each participant will sign a consent form based on a standard format (see [Attachment 4](#)). Participants will receive information via one of the platforms used to recruit participants for the trial, and we will go through this again at the beginning of each user test appointment.

Data Protection Impact Assessment - DPIA

We do not intend to directly elicit health-related information from participants during this user test. It is also unlikely that health information will be indirectly provided by participants given the task and the topic of the user test. Therefore, we do not deem it necessary to undertake a full DPIA assessment.

References

- (EPOC), C. E. P. a. O. o. C. (2018). "Reporting the effects of an intervention in EPOC reviews." EPOC Resources for review authors, . Retrieved 07.09.2022, 2022.
- Balshem, H., et al. (2011). "GRADE guidelines: 3. Rating the quality of evidence." Journal of clinical epidemiology **64**(4): 401-406.
- Byambasuren, O., et al. (2021). "The effect of eye protection on SARS-CoV-2 transmission: a systematic review." Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control **10**(1): 1-7.
- Chu, D. K., et al. (2020). "Physical distancing, face masks, and eye protection to prevent person-to-person transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis." The lancet **395**(10242): 1973-1987.
- Coroneo, M. T. and P. J. Collignon (2021). "SARS-CoV-2: eye protection might be the missing key." The Lancet Microbe **2**(5): e173-e174.
- DePoy, E. and L. Gitlin (2016). Chapter 20 - Statistical analysis for experimental-type designs. Introduction to Research (Fifth Edition): Understanding and Applying Multiple Strategies: 282-310.
- Fretheim, A., et al. (2022). "The Glasses Against transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in the community (GLASSY) trial: A pragmatic randomized trial (study protocol)." medRxiv.
- Glenton, C., et al. (2010). "Presenting the results of Cochrane Systematic Reviews to a consumer audience: a qualitative study." Medical Decision Making **30**(5): 566-577.
- Glenton, C., et al. (2006). "Summaries of findings, descriptions of interventions, and information about adverse effects would make reviews more informative." Journal of clinical epidemiology **59**(8): 770-778.
- Hultcrantz, M., et al. (2017). "The GRADE Working Group clarifies the construct of certainty of evidence." Journal of clinical epidemiology **87**: 4-13.
- Jefferson, T., et al. (2020). "Physical interventions to interrupt or reduce the spread of respiratory viruses." Cochrane database of systematic reviews(11).
- Maxcy, K. F. (1919). "The transmission of infection through the eye." Journal of the American Medical Association **72**(9): 636-639.
- Morville, P. "User Experience Design. honeycomb model." 07.09.2022.
- Munthe-Kaas, H. (2021). Exploring the development of the GRADE-CERQual and TRANSFER approaches to enhance accountability for reasonableness in evidence-informed decision-making

processes. [Institute of Health & Society, Faculty of Medicine](#). Oslo, University of Oslo. **Doctor Philosophiae**.

Richardson, S., et al. (2017). "Think aloud" and "Near live" usability testing of two complex clinical decision support tools." [International journal of medical informatics](#) **106**: 1-8.

Ritchie, J. and L. Spencer (2002). Qualitative data analysis for applied policy research. [Analyzing qualitative data](#), Routledge: 187-208.

Rosenbaum, S. (2010). Improving the user experience of evidence. A design approach to evidence-informed health care. Oslo, Oslo College of Architecture and Design.

Rosenbaum, S. (2010). Improving the user experience of evidence. A design approach to evidence-informed health care. Oslo, Oslo College of Architecture and Design. **PhD thesis**.

Rosenbaum, S. E., et al. (2008). "User experiences of evidence-based online resources for health professionals: user testing of The Cochrane Library." [BMC medical informatics and decision making](#) **8**(1): 1-11.

Santesso, N., et al. (2009). "A new format for plain language summaries: does it improve understanding, and is it useful and preferable." [A Randomized Trial](#) **17**.

UserTesting. (2022). "Moderated vs. unmoderated usability testing: the pros and cons." Retrieved 19.10.2022, 200.

Witteman, H. O., et al. (2015). "User-centered design and the development of patient decision aids: protocol for a systematic review." [Systematic reviews](#) **4**(1): 1-8.

Woloshin, S. and L. M. Schwartz (2011). "Communicating data about the benefits and harms of treatment: a randomized trial." [Annals of internal medicine](#) **155**(2): 87-96.

Attachment 1. Message lab user test platform selection

Initial selection of platforms to test

We will search the internet for user testing platforms (using the term “user testing platforms” and “user testing online” and create a list of platforms that fit the following criteria:

- Offer moderated and unmoderated user testing
- Allow for qualitative data collection (e.g., record screen and/or audio)
- Pool of participants for recruitment
- Allow for recruitment of own participants
- Custom questions and feedback sections
- It is possible to access the platform online or download and install the tool
- The participants and users do not require specific computing expertise, hardware or other resources
- Option to test static content and/or prototypes

We will also search websites that review user testing platforms (e.g., Nielsen Norman Group, uxdesign.cc).

Of the identified platforms meeting the above criteria, we will choose two platforms to evaluate in a pilot project. This initial selection will be based on reviews of the platforms and interactions with the platforms via trial subscriptions.

In the pilot project, we will explore user perception of a text to be used in a randomized trial (Message Lab, see XXX). We will recruit 10 users who will be randomized to either platform 1 or platform 2 (alternatively, we will randomly recruit 5 users from each platform). The users will be presented with the text and instructed to give their first impressions of the text. They will then be presented with a number of follow-up questions regarding language, wording, and format of the text.

Platform selection

We will choose a tool to use in future randomized trials in Message Lab based on feature analysis, useability, participant satisfaction and price. Each of these factors will be rated by at least two researchers involved in choosing the platform using a scale of 1 to 5, and the ratings will be combined to come up with a final score.

Feature analysis

The platform will be required to have the characteristics outlined above in the search criteria. In addition, platforms will be rated according to whether they also offer the following features:

- Automatic transcription
- Qualitative data analysis
- Observation room
- Allow participants to highlight and comment on difficult words or phrases
- Allow for follow-up interviews with participants

Useability

The researcher responsible for setting up the user test will fill out the System Usability Scale (REF) which includes the following 10 questions with five response options for each question:

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.

2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3. I thought the system was easy to use.
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.
9. I felt very confident using the system.
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

Responses can be given using a five-point scale from 1-strongly agree to 5-strongly disagree.

Participant assessment

We will include the Single Ease Question¹ at the end of the user test to evaluate participants' perceived ease of use: "Overall, how difficult or easy was the task to complete?" We will make it clear that we are asking about the platform, not the user test itself. The answer will be rated using a seven-point scale from 1 -very difficult to 7- very easy.

Price

The price of the two platforms will be compared after comparing the other three factors.

¹ Sauro, J., Dumas, J.S.: Comparison of three one-question, post-task usability questionnaires. In: Olsen Jr., D.R., Arthur, R.B., Hinckley, K., Morris, M.R., Hudson, S.E., Greenberg, S. (eds.) Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 1599–1608. ACM, New York (2009).

Attachment 2. Interview guide for communicating certainty user test

Moderated user test

Semi-structured interview guide

Participant number	
Date	
Researcher	
Observer	
Message number	

Checklist

1. Consent form signed
2. Information about user test and what is being tested
3. Observation and note taking
4. Interview guide

Introduction

Go through consent form (sent beforehand). Any problems or questions?

Who are we? What do we do? What is the purpose of this user test? What will the findings be used for?

Right of the participant to stop test at any time

What do we do with our notes after?

Questions?

Instructions

A short bit of repetition before we begin.

No right or wrong answer

You are not being tested, it is our material we are testing. There are no right or wrong answers to our questions. If you think something is easy or difficult, clear or confusing, if you understand or don't understand, we just want to know about it.

Think out loud

Think out loud. Tell me what you are thinking, what you see, what you find confusing or surprising, even the least little bit. For instance:

- What you are looking at, describe your experience of it.
- If you are unsure about anything
- If you are surprised by anything
- If there are things you don't understand, just say "I don't know what this means..."

My role

My role is to ask questions. But, since it is your opinion we are interested in, I will be otherwise saying as little as possible. You can ask me questions, but I won't be answering them. If you like, I can answer them as well as I can when we are finished.

1	<p>First impressions</p> <p>Before I give you the document, I want your first immediate impression, your spontaneous reaction to it when I show you them. Don't think, just tell me the first thing that comes into your head when you see them.</p> <p>> Now give them version M6 of the text.</p> <p>What is your first spontaneous reaction?</p>
2	<p>Follow-up questions</p> <p>Please reread the public health message below and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked? - Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information? - Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)? - Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify. - Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify. - Did you understand the text? - Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text? - Was the text easy to read, why or why not? - Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you? - Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?
3	<p>Now give them version M4 of the text.</p> <p>Please read the text (see appendix XX)</p> <p>What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind. This can be related to content, format, font, language or anything.</p> <p>-</p>
4	<p>Now please reread the text and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information? - Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)? - Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify. - Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify. - Did you understand the text? - Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text? - Was the text easy to read, why or why not? - Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you? - Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?
5	<p>Now give them version M1 of the text.</p> <p>Please read the text (see appendix XX)</p> <p>What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind. This can be related to content, format, font, language or anything.</p>
6	<p>Now please reread the text and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked? - Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information? - Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)? - Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify. - Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify. - Did you understand the text? - Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text? - Was the text easy to read, why or why not? - Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you? - Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?
7	<p>Now give them the list of trial questions.</p> <p>Please read the text (see appendix XX)</p> <p>What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind. This can be related to content, format, font, language or anything.</p>
8	<p>Now please reread the text and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked? - Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)? - Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify. - Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify. - Did you understand the text? - Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text? - Was the text easy to read, why or why not? - Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you? - Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?
9	<p>Now give them the document with text from hyperlinks and hover text.</p> <p>Please read the text (see appendix XX)</p> <p>What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind. This can be related to content, format, font, language or anything.</p>
10	<p>Now please reread the text and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked? - Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information? - Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)? - Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify. - Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify. - Did you understand the text? - Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text? - Was the text easy to read, why or why not? - Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you? - Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?

Unmoderated user test

Text provided to participants (after consent form is signed)

Thank you for participating in this user test. A group of researchers working at the Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health will be conducting a study:

- To compare the effects of three ways of communicating the overall uncertainty of the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID and
- To compare the effects of including the margin of error (confidence interval) compared to not including it.

Before we begin the trial, we would like to see how participants perceive the language and format of the text we provide to trial participants. In this user test you will be asked to imagine yourself in a scenario. You will then be presented with a public health message. You will be asked to give feedback on the text you are provided. You will then be given a list of questions related to the public health message you read. You will be asked to give feedback on the questions.

Steps 1-10 in the box above will be available on the platform. Participants will work their way from text to text with corresponding questions.

Attachment 3. Instructions for self-moderated user test

Thank you for participating in this user test. It will take approximately 30 minutes to complete.

What is this about?

A group of researchers working at the Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health will be conducting a study:

- To compare the effects of three ways of communicating the overall uncertainty of the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID and
- To compare the effects of including the margin of error (confidence interval) compared to not including it.

Before we begin the trial, we would like to see how participants perceive the language and format of the text we provide to trial participants. Your input will help us improve the trial materials, leading to a better-quality study.

What will I be doing?

In this user test you will be asked to imagine yourself in a scenario. You will then be presented with three public health messages and a set of follow-up questions about each of these message texts. Then you will then be given a list of trial questions related to the public health messages and be asked to give feedback on the questions. Finally, you will be given some extra text that is found via hover and hyperlinks in the text and asked to give feedback on these texts.

In total you will be presented with five pieces of text that you will give feedback on. For each text you will be asked to give first impressions (your spontaneous reaction to the text), and then asked several follow-up questions.

Please reply with your own opinions, not how you think other people might respond.

Start user test

Scenario:

Imagine you hear that glasses may reduce your chance of becoming infected with COVID. You go online to find out more information and find a website that says...

1 First impressions

Before you read the document, be aware that the first question will be about your first impressions. So try to pay attention to them as you start to read.

>>> Read Section 1: version M6 of the text.

See appendix 1

What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind related to:

- Content
- Format
- Font
- Language
- Anything else

1 Follow-up questions

Please reread Section 1: version M6 of the text and answer the following questions:

Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information?

Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?

Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify.		
Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify.		
Did you understand the text?		
Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text?		
Was the text easy to read, why or why not?		
Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you?		
Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?		

2 First impressions

Before you read the document, be aware that the first question will be about your first impressions. So try to pay attention to them as you start to read

>>> Read Section 2: version M4 of the text.

See appendix 1

See appendix 2

What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind related to:

- Content
- Format
- Font
- Language
- Anything else

Commented [SR1]: @Heather Eileen Menzies Munthe-
Kaas is this a typo?

2 Follow-up questions

Now please reread Section 2: version M4 of the text and answer the following questions:

Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information?		
Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?		
Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify.		
Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify.		

Did you understand the text?		
Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text?		
Was the text easy to read, why or why not?		
Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you?		
Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?		

3 First impressions

Before you read the document, be aware that the first question will be about your first impressions. So try to pay attention to them as you start to read

>>> Read Section 3: version M1 of the text.

See appendix 1

What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind related to:

- Content
- Format
- Font
- Language
- Anything else

3 Follow-up questions

Now please reread Section 3: version M1 of the text and answer the following questions:

Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most		
--	--	--

important information?		
Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?		
Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify.		
Are there any words or phrases that are confusing? Please specify.		
Did you understand the text?		
Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text?		
Was the text easy to read, why or why not?		
Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you?		
Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?		

4 First impressions

Before you read the document, be aware that the first question will be about your first impressions. So try to pay attention to them as you start to read

>>> Read Section 4: the list of trial questions.

You do not need to answer the questions in this list. We would like you comment on the wording and formatting of the questions.

See appendix 1

What are your first impressions? Please write the first thing that comes to mind related to:

- Content
- Format
- Font
- Language
- Anything else

4 Follow-up questions

Now please reread Section 4: the list of trial questions and answer the following questions:

Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information?

Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?

Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify.

Are there any words or phrases that are

confusing? Please specify.		
Did you understand the text?		
Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text?		
Was the text easy to read, why or why not?		
Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you?		
Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?		
Does the text you read earlier (versions M6, M1 and M4) contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked?		

5 First impressions

Before you read the document, be aware that the first question will be about your first impressions. So try to pay attention to them as you start to read

>>> [Read Section 5: text found via hover and hyperlinks.](#)

See appendix 1

What are your first impressions? Please write		
---	--	--

<p>the first thing that comes to mind related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content - Format - Font - Language - Anything else 		
<p>5 Follow-up questions Now please reread Section 5: text found via hover and hyperlinks and answer the following questions:</p>		
<p>Does the text contain the necessary information for you to understand the questions being asked?</p>		
<p>Is the text formatted so that you can easily find the most important information?</p>		
<p>Can you easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)?</p>		
<p>Are there any words or phrases that you do not understand? Please specify.</p>		
<p>Are there any words or phrases that are</p>		

confusing? Please specify.		
Did you understand the text?		
Were you able to find the information you needed to understand the text?		
Was the text easy to read, why or why not?		
Did you feel like the text was targeting you or someone like you?		
Is there anything you don't like about the format of the text?		

Attachment 4. Consent form for user testing

What is the aim of the user test?

To evaluate the language, content and format of the messages to be used in a randomized study to evaluate the effect of communicating certainty in public health messages.

Who are the participants?

- English speakers

How is the test conducted?

- The entire test takes approximately thirty minutes
- Participants will read through instructions and relevant text and provide feedback to questions regarding the readability and understandability of the text.
- Participation in the test is voluntary. You can withdraw from the test at any time.

How will we use the findings of the user testing?

- We will revise the text in Appendix 1 according to feedback from the user test.

Do you have any questions?

Consent

I have received written and oral information and am willing to participate in the study.

yes no

Other members of the research team can listen to the audio recording.

yes no

NAME (Block letters):

Date

Signature